

Vectorial complex division

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Given $\vec{v}, \vec{u} \in \mathbb{R}^n$ with $\vec{v} = \|\vec{v}\|\hat{v}$ and $\vec{u} = \|\vec{u}\|\hat{u}$, we can write

$$\ln \vec{v} = \ln (\|\vec{v}\|\hat{v}) = \ln \|\vec{v}\| + \ln \hat{v}$$

Now let's take the plane spanned by the two vectors: $S = \langle \vec{v}, \vec{u} \rangle$. In this plane we can fix a Gauß plane in order to calculate $\ln \hat{v}$:

$$\ln \hat{v} = (\angle \hat{v} + \gamma)i$$

where $\gamma \in \mathbb{R}$ is an arbitrary constant, derived from the fact we cannot know the real phase of \hat{v} in the Gauß plane, since it depends on how we fixed the axis.

We cannot compute the phase of \hat{v} but we can easily compute the difference of phase of two versors: it is the angle between the two

$$(\angle \hat{v} + \gamma) - (\angle \hat{u} + \gamma) = \angle \hat{v} - \angle \hat{u} = \widehat{\hat{v}\hat{u}}$$

and from the formula of dot product:

$$\hat{v} \cdot \hat{u} = \|\hat{v}\|\|\hat{u}\| \cos(\widehat{\hat{v}\hat{u}})$$

$$\widehat{\hat{v}\hat{u}} = \pm \cos^{-1} \frac{\hat{v} \cdot \hat{u}}{\|\hat{v}\|\|\hat{u}\|} = \pm \cos^{-1}(\hat{v} \cdot \hat{u})$$

Finally we can compute the complex division of the two vectors, by means of its logarithm:

$$\begin{aligned} \ln \frac{\vec{v}}{\vec{u}} &= \ln \|\vec{v}\| + \ln \hat{v} - (\ln \|\vec{u}\| + \ln \hat{u}) = \ln \frac{\|\vec{v}\|}{\|\vec{u}\|} + (\ln \hat{v} - \ln \hat{u}) = \\ &= \ln \frac{\|\vec{v}\|}{\|\vec{u}\|} \pm \cos^{-1}(\hat{v} \cdot \hat{u})i \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\vec{v}}{\vec{u}} &= e^{\ln \frac{\|\vec{v}\|}{\|\vec{u}\|} \pm \cos^{-1}(\hat{v} \cdot \hat{u})i} = \frac{\|\vec{v}\|}{\|\vec{u}\|} e^{\pm \cos^{-1}(\hat{v} \cdot \hat{u})i} = \\ &= \frac{\|\vec{v}\|}{\|\vec{u}\|} \left(\cos \left(\pm \cos^{-1}(\hat{v} \cdot \hat{u}) \right) + \sin \left(\pm \cos^{-1}(\hat{v} \cdot \hat{u}) \right) i \right) = \\ &= \frac{\|\vec{v}\|}{\|\vec{u}\|} \left(\hat{v} \cdot \hat{u} \pm \sqrt{1 - (\hat{v} \cdot \hat{u})^2} i \right) \end{aligned}$$

For the last step was used the following identity:

$$\sin \cos^{-1} x = \sqrt{\sin^2 \cos^{-1} x} = \sqrt{1 - \cos^2 \cos^{-1} x} = \sqrt{1 - x^2}$$

1 Properties

Division of a vector by itself

$$\frac{\vec{v}}{\vec{v}} = \frac{\|\vec{v}\|}{\|\vec{v}\|} \left(\hat{v} \cdot \hat{v} \pm \sqrt{1 - (\hat{v} \cdot \hat{v})^2} i \right)$$

and since $\hat{v} \cdot \hat{v} = \|\hat{v}\|^2 = 1$

$$\frac{\vec{v}}{\vec{v}} = 1 \pm \sqrt{1 - 1}i = 1$$

Division by identity There is no unity vector, but all versors are unitar:

$$\frac{\vec{v}}{\hat{u}} = \frac{\|\vec{v}\|}{\|\hat{u}\|} \left(\hat{v} \cdot \hat{u} \pm \sqrt{1 - (\hat{v} \cdot \hat{u})^2} i \right)$$

we don't know the value of $\hat{v} \cdot \hat{u}$, but we can compute the module of the division:

$$\left| \frac{\vec{v}}{\hat{u}} \right| = \|\vec{v}\| \left((\hat{v} \cdot \hat{u})^2 + 1 - (\hat{v} \cdot \hat{u})^2 \right) = \|\vec{v}\|$$

So the module is the same of the magnitude of \vec{v} , as expected. As for the direction, it is simple to observe that for each choice of the Gauß plane axis, there exist a versor for which the direction is the same of \vec{v} .

Inverse It's simple to observe as swapping numerator and denominator makes the module inverse and doesn't affect the phase. So

$$\left| \frac{\hat{u}}{\vec{v}} \right| = \frac{1}{\|\vec{v}\|}$$